

Multilingual Named Entity Recognition in Tweets using Wikidata

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Named Entity Recognition (NER) is the process of detecting named mentions (e.g. persons, locations and organizations) in a text. NER is an essential subtask in several NLP applications such as machine translation, summarization and virtual assistance. While high-resource languages have received enormous focus over the last two decades, NER for low-resource languages is still under-explored due to the lack of resources and the cost of labeling data needed to train supervised models. Furthermore, NER for social media data is even harder (Mishra and Diesner, 2016; Mishra, 2019) because of the linguistic diversity in social media text. We present and compare monolingual and multilingual NER techniques that require no labeled data, which encourages the development of downstream applications for low-resource languages. Our evaluation on nine different languages shows that we can achieve a high precision NER model across multiple languages.

We exploit Wikidata¹, a multilingual knowledge graph of about 88M entities in several languages. We process Wikidata to create a named-entity dictionary that we use as a lookup to annotate tweets in 65 languages, up to one million tweets per language that are uniformly distributed across 21 day period. We use a trie based algorithm to efficiently store and annotate the presence of longest named entities in tweets in linear time. While gazetteers (Mishra and Diesner, 2016) have been used in the past as features this is the word uses Wikidata to generate synthetic training data. While the lookup approach leads to high precision, it cannot recognize unseen entities. We therefore train BiLSTM taggers, similar to Lample et al. (2016), that use the lookup-based labeled text as the training data and exploit multilingual GloVe embeddings based on tweets². Since, unigram identification is noisy and has proportion in the training data, we restrict the detected mentions to contain two or more tokens. However, we replicate the training data to generate tweets of corresponding unigram mentions by using only the first words in the person entities. We train our NER taggers in two setups, monolingual, one tagger per language, and multilingual, where we train only one tagger after merging the training data of 65 languages. We also experiment the use of augmented training data by adding WikiANN (Pan et al., 2017), a multilingual NER dataset that was automatically generated based on Wikipedia. The addition of WikiANN allows the model to learn a more general structure of named entities without using any human labeled data.

Table 1 reports the performance of the lookup, monolingual-training and multilingual-training setups when tested on nine languages (without using any labeled data) using publicly available datasets, namely CoNLL-02 (Tjong Kim Sang, 2002), CoNLL-03 (Tjong Kim Sang and De Meulder, 2003), xLIME³, SSEA (Singh, 2008), JRC⁴, SSEA⁵ and Code-Switching-2018 (CS-18)⁶, in terms of entity-level micro-average F1-scores for persons, locations and organizations. The multilingual approach yields the best performance in four languages, while the addition of WikiANN always helps except in Arabic. The results encourage further research in the multilingual direction without the use of labeled data. We find that the low performance on non latin script languages is likely due to under-representation of words belonging to these languages in the multilingual embedding. Our work can allow identifying popular named entities in social media corpora across multiple languages.

Language	English	German	Dutch	Spanish	French	Italian	Turkish	Hindi	Arabic
Testing Dataset	CoNLL-03	CoNLL-03	CoNLL-02	CoNLL-02	xLIME	xLIME	JRC	SEAS	CS-18
Lookup	36.6	22.8	36.8	29.7	15.6	23.3	22.9	20.4	16.7
Mono Training	40.2	35.5	39.4	27.4	27.7	29.3	24.8	11.8	22.8
Mul Training	38.3	36.6	43.2	29.1	26.4	28.9	28.0	9.8	14.0
Mono Training + WikiANN	47.2	41.2	55.4	37.6	30.3	28.4	27.8	14.0	21.9
Mul Training + WikiANN	43.2	39.6	52.8	44.0	32.6	25.4	28.6	8.3	11.3

Table 1: Entity-Level Micro-Average F1-scores for the PERSON, LOCATION and ORGANIZATION types

[†]This research was carried out during an internship at Twitter.

¹https://wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page

²We also experiment with fastText (Bojanowski et al., 2017) and Polyglot (<https://polyglot.readthedocs.io>), where the performance of tweet embeddings is comparable to the former and better than the latter.

³https://github.com/lrei/xlime_twitter_corpus

⁴http://optima.jrc.it/Resources/2014_JRC_Twitter_TR_NERdataset.zip

⁵<http://ltrc.iit.ac.in/ner-ssea-08/index.cgi?topic=5>

⁶<https://code-switching.github.io/2018/>

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